

Development of a Tool for Automated Integration of Mapillary and OpenStreetMap Data

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Abstract

OpenStreetMap (OSM) has established itself as a crucial open-source geospatial data platform, with applications in several areas. However, the heterogeneity in the completeness and updating of OSM data requires the search for efficient enrichment methods. Platforms such as Mapillary, which provide extensive sets of georeferenced images, represent a valuable source to complement OSM. This study proposes the development of an automated tool for the conflation of Mapillary and OpenStreetMap data, with the objective of identifying and extracting missing information in OSM from Mapillary data, automating the process of spatial comparison and data conversion.

The tool was developed using Python and the mapillary, osmnx and geopandas libraries. The conflation process involves defining the study area and temporal filter for Mapillary images, loading a previously created compatibility table between OSM tags and Mapillary attributes, downloading the selected OSM and Mapillary data, creating buffers for spatial comparison, identifying and eliminating overlapping elements, converting the remaining Mapillary data to the OSM labeling system, and exporting the conflated data.

The results demonstrate the tool's ability to identify missing elements in OSM, such as traffic signs and speed limit, from Mapillary data. The quality of the results, however, depends on factors such as the coverage and quality of the images, the accuracy of the geographic positioning, and the temporal restriction of the images, which, although mitigating the inclusion of obsolete elements, can limit the identification of valid elements that were not detected by Mapillary.

The developed tool represents a promising initial step towards automating the conflation of OSM and Mapillary data, with potential for future improvements such as code optimization, the development of a web interface to expand access, and the search for solutions to the dependency on libraries with limited support. Despite its limitations, the tool shows potential to contribute significantly to the updating and enrichment of OSM, especially in regions with low contribution density, encouraging user participation and promoting the improvement of the quality of open-source geospatial data.